

Health Information Outreach Using an Interdisciplinary Model

Midwest Chapter/Medical Library
Association 2025 Annual Conference

Darlene Kaskie, Associate Director

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Network of the
National Library of Medicine

National Institutes of Health
Nation's leading research agency

National Library of Medicine
World's largest biomedical library

Network of the National Library of Medicine
Outreach program of the NLM

Regions, Offices, and Centers
7 Regional Medical Libraries
3 National Offices
4 National Centers

nnlm.gov

Objectives

SAG development

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graph TD; A[SAG development] --> B[SAG programs]; B --> C[SAG impact];
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SAG programs

SAG impact

State Advisory Groups - SAGs

LISTEN

BUILD

LEARN

SAG Members

Goals of the SAG Program

Health Scan

County Health Rankings & Roadmaps

Logic Model

Michigan SAG

Inputs	Outputs	Outcomes
Funds for contracted professional to develop the kit Input from Michigan mental health experts Funds for printing and distributing kit to libraries Time and work on the part of Advisory Group members and NNLM staff for content development, distribution, promotion, and evaluation of kit	Mental Health Resource Kit Promotion and distribution of kit to NNLM member libraries in Michigan Evaluation of kit Periodic revisions in response to feedback	Greater comfort level responding to mental health needs Greater awareness of resources Future phase: Develop partnerships with external organizations that can act as conduits for sharing the kit with other audiences beyond libraries

Deliverables

Crisis & Mental Health Resources

Call #988 or scan the QR code for more information!

NAMI **NIH** National Library of Medicine
MINNESOTA MINNESOTA STATE ADVISORY GROUP

Smile!

A Guide to Healthy & Happy Teeth

Mental Health Information Community Partnerships Toolkit

Network of the National Library of Medicine, Region 6

KNOW YOUR FLOW

This library is proud to offer **FREE** period products

Michigan Mental Health Training Kit

NNLM DISCOVERY

Outcome Data

[KnowYourFlow](#) user analytics as of December 2024. Source: Aunt Flow

Community Impact

Member Survey

Survey Results

80% of respondents agreed/strongly agreed that working with their SAG provided insights into state and community needs not easily identified in other ways (N=32).

93% of respondents agreed/strongly agreed that a targeted project that addresses a health disparity need was selected (N=37).

78% of respondents agreed/strongly agreed that serving as a SAG member increased their awareness of the NNLM Region 6 mission, resources, and services (N=31).

Lessons Learned

1

Meeting Schedule

3

Group Facilitation

2

**Inter-SAG
Communication**

4

**Project
Management**

Conclusion

Success

Addressed
specific
health
disparities

Expanded
access to
health
information

Developed a
replicable
framework for
community
health
initiatives

Learn More!

STATE ADVISORY GROUPS FINAL REPORT

NETWORK OF THE NATIONAL LIBRARY OF MEDICINE, REGION 6
Hardin Library for the Health Sciences, University of Iowa
October 6, 2025

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